

Role of Serum Magnesium as a Prognostic Indicator in Diabetic Critically Ill Patients

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Critical illness is a state of ill health with vital organ dysfunction, the severity is assessed by APACHE II. Diabetes Mellitus commonest co-morbid in critically patient characterised by hyperglycaemia leading to macro and micro-vascular complications. Magnesium is cofactor for wide range of enzymes, transporters and nucleic acids and essential for normal neuromuscular activity, normal cellular function, replication, and energy metabolism and plays a key role in regulating insulin action, insulin-mediated-glucose uptake vascular tone. Hypomagnesaemia in Diabetes is due to impaired tubular magnesium re-absorption, osmotic diuresis and acidosis.

Materials & Methods: Retrospective study for 18 months at SSMC, Tumakuru, by collecting data from MRD, analysed for age, sex, Magnesium, Sugar, APACHE II, Need and Duration of ventilator, ICU stay and mortality.

Results: 73 (48.6%) were Diabetics and 77(51.4%) were Nondiabetics. Mean age is 60 in Hypomagnesemic diabetics, 63 in Normomagnesemic diabetics and 55 in Nondiabetics. Male preponderance of 58.9% in both Diabetic and Non diabetics. Prevalence of Hypomagnesaemia is 50.6% in Diabetic and 35.06% in Nondiabetics and this relation between hypomagnesemia and Diabetics is highly statistically significant as p-value is <0.001. Mean APACHE II in Hypomagnesemic diabetics is 24.8, Normomagnesemic diabetics 21.5 and Nondiabetics 16.9. Mean ICU stay in Hypomagnesemic diabetics is 5.9 days, Normomagnesemic diabetics 3.5 days and Nondiabetics 2.8 days. 41.1% Hypomagnesemia diabetics, 15.06% Normomagnesemic diabetics and 32.46% Nondiabetic needed ventilator. Mean Duration is 99.9hrs in Hypomagnesemic diabetics, 31.2 hrs in Normomagnesemic diabetics and 39.72 hrs in Nondiabetics. Mean Mortality in Hypomagnesemic diabetics 25.4, Normomagnesemic diabetics 19.8 and Nondiabetics 21.6. Relation between hypomagnesemia and severity of critical illness in Diabetics is highly statistically significant as p-value <0.001 in ICU Duration, p-value <0.001 in Need for Ventilator and p-value <0.001 in Duration of Ventilation.

Conclusion: Hypomagnesemia is commonly observed in Diabetic critically ill patients and can be used as a prognostic indicator to assess the severity of critical illness.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a common metabolic disorder sharing the phenotype of hyperglycaemia either due to reduced insulin secretion or decreased glucose utilization or increased glucose production. Diabetes mellitus can lead to microvascular complications like retinopathy, neuropathy, microangiopathy and nephropathy¹. Critical illness is a state

of ill health with vital organ dysfunction, a high risk of imminent death if care is not provided and the potential for reversibility. Severity of critically illness is assessed by APACHE II (Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II) introduced in 1985 a modification of the original APACHE developed in 1981. APACHE-II has three domains: "Acute Physiology", "Chronic Health Evaluation"

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and “Age” reflected by the acronym APACHE. First domain relates with acute physiological changes within first 24 hours. Total maximum score will be 71 calculated as 12 physiological variables (12 x4), Temperature, Mean arterial blood pressure, Heart rate, Respiratory rate, Arterial oxygenation, Arterial pH, Serum sodium, Serum potassium, Serum Creatinine, Haematocrit, Total Leukocyte Count and GCS (0 to 12) and Chronic health problems (0 to 5) including severe organ insufficiency or immunocompromised and Age (0 to 6)². Magnesium is the major intracellular divalent cation essential for normal neuromuscular activity and normal cellular function, replication, and energy metabolism as magnesium is an important cofactor for wide range of enzymes, transporters, and nucleic acids. Normal serum magnesium is 0.7–1 mmol/L (1.7–2.4 mg/dL) of which 30% is protein-bound and 15% is loosely complexed to phosphate and other anions. Total body magnesium is mainly located in bone and intracellularly in mineral phase, only 1% of body magnesium resides in the Extra Cellular Fluid. Regulation of serum magnesium is achieved mainly by control of renal magnesium reabsorption as 20% of filtered magnesium is reabsorbed in the proximal tubule, 60% in cortical thick ascending limb of loop of henle and 5–10% in the DCT³. Hyperglycaemia directly impairs tubular magnesium reabsorption and persistent glycosuria with osmotic diuresis leads to magnesium wasting and contributes to Hypomagnesaemia in poorly controlled diabetic patients. Hypomagnesaemia is also aggravated by diabetic acidosis due to rapid shift of magnesium from extracellular into intracellular compartment⁴. Intracellular magnesium plays a key role in regulating insulin action, insulin-mediated-glucose uptake and vascular tone. Reduced intracellular magnesium result in a defective tyrosine kinase activity, post receptorial impairment in insulin action and worsening of insulin resistance in diabetic patients⁵. This study was conducted as several studies from all over India by Vineesha et.al⁶ from Delhi, Ramesh et.al⁷ from Ap, Ashok et.al⁸from Telangana, Prasad et.al⁹ from Karnataka highlighted the significant association of Hypomagnesemia with severity of critically ill patients in the form of adverse outcomes and mortality and Diabetes mellitus being the most common comorbid among them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Retrospective observational study conducted between January 2023 to June 2024 at tertiary care centre, Sri Siddhartha Medical College and Research Hospital, Tumakuru, Karnataka. After taking the clearance from the institution Scientific and Ethical committee study was conducted by collecting the case records from the Medical Records Department of the institution. All critically ill Patients of more than 18 years admitted under Department of General Medicine satisfying the criteria of more than or equal to 10 APACHE II score were included in the study. APACHE II scoring was calculated using online software (<https://clincalc.com/IcuMortality/APACHEI.aspx>) . Patients with diuretic use for more than 6weeks or on aminoglycoside, patients who underwent gastro intestinal surgery, having malabsorption, pancreatitis and who received magnesium supplementation over 48 hours prior to admission, chronic kidney disease were excluded the study . Patient details including Age, Sex, history of Diabetes Mellitus, APACHE II score, Serum Magnesium estimated by formazan dye method , Blood Sugar estimated by oxidase hydroperoxide method, Need for Ventilator support, Duration of ICU stay and Mortality were recorded in the prescribed proforma. Patients with Serum Magnesium less than 1.7mg/dl were considered as Hypomagnesaemia and with Serum Magnesium 1.7-2.4mg/dl were considered as Normomagnesaemia. Patients with Blood Sugar more than 200mg/dl and history of diabetes on treatment were considered as Diabetics. Collected data was entered in Micro soft Excel sheet and analyzed using SPSS software.

RESULTS

There were 150 critically ill patients in this study conducted between January 2023 to June 2024, 73 (48.6%) were Diabetics remaining 77 (51.4%) Nondiabetics who were considered as controls. Majority Diabetics were 43 (58.9%) Male and 30 (41.1%) were Female. Majority Non diabetics were 46 (59.7%) also male and 31(40.3%) were female. Table 1. Fig. 1.

Gender wise distribution Diabetics and Nondiabetics in critically ill patients

Table 1.

Gender	Diabetics	Nondiabetics
Male	43 (58.9%)	46(58.9%)
Female	30 (41.1%)	31(40.3%)
Total	73 (100%)	77(100%)

Figure. 1

Age of Diabetics ranges from 23 to 87 years with a Mean of 62.3 ± 16 years. Majority 28.7% were in 61-70 years age group followed by 21.9% in 71-80 years, 17.8% in 51-60 years, 5.4% in < 30 years and 4.1% in > 80 years group. Age of Nondiabetics ranges from 19 to 87 years with a Mean of 62.3 ± 16 years. Majority 27.7% were also in the age group 60-70 years followed by 21% in 70-80 years, 18.7% in 50-60 years, 5.4% in < 30 years and 4.9% in > 80 years group. Table 2. Fig 2

Age wise distribution of Diabetic and non diabetics

Table. 2

Age group Distribution	Diabetic	Nondiabetic
<30 years	4(5.4%)	4(5.4%)
30-40 years	5(6.9%)	6(7.1%)
41-50 years	11(15.2%)	11(15.2%)
51-60years	13(17.8%)	15(18.7%)
61-70 years	21(28.7%)	21(27.7%)
71-80 years	16	16
>80 years	3	4
Total	73	77

Figure.2

Mean age in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics is 60.13 years compared to 63.2 years in Normomagnesemic Diabetics and 55.9 years in Non-Diabetics. Table 3, Fig 3

Mean Age of Normo and Hypomagnesimic Diabetics and Non Diabetics

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CATEGORY	MEAN
Hypomagnesemic Diabetics	60.13
Normomagnesemic Diabetics	63.2
Nondiabetics	55.94

Hypomagnesemia in diabetes.
 Normal magnesium in diabetes.
 Non diabetes

There was Normomagnesimia in 71 (39.6%), Hypomagnesaemia in 54(39.6%), and Hypermagnesimia in 15 (39.6%) in all critically ill patients. There was Normomagnesimia in 29 (39.8%) and Hypomagnesaemia in 37 (50.6%)in Diabetics and Normomagnesimia in 42 (55%) and Hypomagnesaemia in 27(35.2%) in Nondiabetics. Table 4. Fig 4

Serum Magnesium in Diabetic and Non Diabetic

Table-4

Serum Mg	DIABETICS	NONDIABETICS	P- value <0.001
LOW	35(50.6%)	27(35.2%)	
NORMAL	29(39.8%)	42(55%)	
HIGH	7(9.6%)	8(9.8%)	
TOTAL	73 (100)	77 (100)	

Figure-4

APACHE II score ranged from 11 to 49 in Diabetics with Mean of 21.8 ± 8.1 compared to ranged from 11 to 44 in Nondiabetics with Mean of 16.9 ± 7.6 . Table 5. Fig 5

Mean APACHE II score in Diabetic and Non-Diabetic

Table-5

Parameter	APACHE Diabetics	APACHE NonDiabetics
Minimum	10	11
Maximum	49	44
Mean \pm SD	21.8 ± 8.1	16.9 ± 7.6

Figure-5

Mean APACHE II in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics is 24.8 compared to 21.5 in Normomagnesemic Diabetics and 16.9 in Non Diabetics. Table 6 Fig 6

Mean APACHE II in Normo and Hypomagnesemic Diabetic and Non Diabetic

Table 6

Figure 6

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CATEGORY	MEAN
Hypomagnesemic Diabetics	24.8
Normomagnesemic Diabetics	21.5
Nondiabetics.	16.9

Mean Duration of ICU stay was more in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics 5.9 days compared to 3.5 in Normomagnesemic Diabetics and 2.7 in Non Diabetics.

Table – 7

Figure - 7

CATEGORY	MEAN	p-value <0.001
Hypomagnesemic Diabetics	5.9 DAYS	
Normomagnesemic Diabetics	3.5 DAYS	
Non-Diabetics	2.7 DAYS	

Need for Ventilation was more in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics 41.1% compared to Normomagnesemic Diabetes 15.6% and NonDiabetics 32.46%. Table.8 Fig. 8

Table – 8

Figure - 8

CATEGORY	NEED FOR VENTILATOR	P-value <0.001
Hypomagnesemic Diabetics	30(41.1%)	
Normomagnesemic Diabetics	11(15.6%)	
Non-Diabetics	25(32.46%)	

Mean Duration of Ventilation was more in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics 99.9 hours compared to Normomagnesemic Diabetics 31.2 and NonDiabetics 30 . Table9 Fig. 9

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Table – 79

CATEGORY	MEAN	
Hypomagnesemic Diabetics	99.9	<0.001
Normomagnesemic Diabetes	31.2	
NonDiabetics	30	

Hypomagnesemic diabetics
 Normomagnesemic diabetics
 Nondiabetics.

Figure - 9

There were 7 deaths in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics and 8 in Normomagnesemic Diabetics.

DISCUSSION

Diabetes mellitus is a major metabolic disorder having microvascular complications leading to retinopathy, nephropathy and neuropathy. Impaired insulin synthesis, insulin resistance, and increased vascular issues are related to magnesium deficiency and Diabetes. High prevalence of Hypomagnesaemia may be attributed to increased urinary loss, osmotic diuresis, low dietary intake or impaired absorption of magnesium compared to healthy individuals. Low levels of magnesium promote endothelial cell dysfunction and thrombogenesis by increasing platelet aggregation and vascular complication. Magnesium has been shown to inhibit platelet activation by inhibiting thromboxaneA2 & interfering with the IIb, IIa receptor complex formation. The influence of magnesium on cell membrane ATPase activity, consequently on intracellular calcium, sodium and potassium metabolism may also play a role in diabetic complications. Hypomagnesaemia also lead to induction of proinflammatory, profibrogenic response and reduction of protective enzymes against oxidative stress and may interfere with normal cell growth and regulation of apoptosis.

There were 48.6% Diabetics compared to 51.4% Non Diabetics in this study which was comparable to 49.8% of diabetics by chawla et al¹⁰. Age and Sex is similar in both groups as Mean age in Diabetic is 58 and 55.94 in Non Diabetics. This mean age is comparable to 56 by Sreelatha N et.al⁵, 44.72 by Girija Menon et.al¹¹, 58.3 by Ravin Devasir et.al¹. Male preponderance of 58.9% in both Diabetic and Nondiabetic in our study. This was compared to 62% Diabetics by Girija Menon et al¹¹, 60% by Ravin et al¹² and 66% NonDiabetics by Girija Menon et al¹¹ 62.5% by Ravin et al¹². Female preponderance was observed in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics and Non Diabetic group in our study. This is compared to study by Sreelatha N et.al⁵. Prevalence of Hypomagnesemia in Diabetics is 50.6% in our study compared to 67% by Solanki et al¹³, 37% at by kumar et al⁸. Mean of Serum Magnesium in Diabetics is 1.83± 0.41

mg/dl with range of 1.2 to 3.3 compared to mean in Non Diabetics 2.05 ± 0.49 mg/dl with range of 1.0 to 4.4. This relation between hypomagnesemia and Diabetics is highly statistically significant as p-value is <0.001. Mean APACHE II in Diabetic is 24.8 compared to 16.9 in Non Diabetic in our study compared to 23 and 21 by kharibam p et al¹⁴. Hypomagnesemic Diabetics has more morbidity in terms of more duration of ICU stay of 5.9 days compared 5.5 days in Hypomagnesemic Non Diabetics. This was comparable to 6.2 days by Solanki et al¹³, 10.6 days by kumar et al⁸. Need for Ventilator in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics was 41% compared to 48% in Non Diabetics. This was compared to 67% by Solanki et al¹³, 73% by kumar et al⁸. Duration of Ventilatory support of 99.9 hours in Hypomagnesemic Diabetics compared to 93 Non Diabetics. This was compared to 117.6 hours by Solanki et al¹³, 189.6 hours by kumar et al⁸. Relation between Hypomagnesemia and severity of critical illness in Diabetics is highly statistically significant as p-value <0.001 in ICU Duration, p-value <0.001 in Need for Ventilator and p-value <0.001 in Duration of Ventilation.

CONCLUSION

Diabetes mellitus is the commonest comorbid in critically ill patient. Prevalence of Hypomagnesemia is also common in diabetic critically ill patients. Hypomagnesemia can be used as a prognostic indicator to assess the severity of critical illness. Hypomagnesemia can lead to muscle weakness and respiratory compromise which may contribute to challenges in weaning patients from mechanical ventilation and prolonging their need for ventilator support. Estimation of serum magnesium in Diabetics is essential to take remedial measures to prevent and to manage the complications of Diabetes Mellitus in all critically ill patients.

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